

Supplementary material

Table A.1. Immune-related adverse events by system and CTCAE (version 5.0) severity

irAE category	Any grade irAEs (CTCAE grade 1–5)		Severe irAEs (CTCAE grade 3–5)	
	N=166	%	N=76	%
Blood and lymphatic system disorders	7	4.2	6	7.9
Cardiac disorders	2	1.2	2	2.6
Endocrine disorders	31	18.7	3	3.9
Gastrointestinal disorders	24	14.5	18	23.7
General disorders and administration site conditions	7	4.2	0	0
Hepatobiliary disorders	20	12	13	17.1
Immune system disorders	4	2.4	4	5.3
Metabolism and nutrition disorders	5	3	1	1.3
Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders	7	4.2	1	1.3
Nervous system disorders	3	1.8	0	0
Renal and urinary disorders	3	1.8	2	2.6
Respiratory, thoracic and mediastinal disorders	32	19.3	19	25
Skin and subcutaneous tissue disorders	21	12.7	7	9.2

Abbreviations: CTCAE, Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events

Figure A.1. Stacked survival curves from treatment start to both the development of severe immune related adverse events (irAEs) and death. A) Transition probabilities from state 1 (treatment initiation) in the sarcopenic group; B) group Transition probabilities from state 1 (treatment initiation) in the sarcopenic group; C) Probability of death after the development of severe irAEs in the sarcopenic ; D) Probability of death after the development of severe irAEs in the sarcopenic group.

C)

Probability of death after the development of a severe irAE in the sarcopenic group

D)

Probability of death after the development of a severe irAE in the non-sarcopenic group

Figure A.2. Stacked survival curves from treatment start to both the development of all immune related adverse events (irAEs) and death. A) Transition probabilities from state 1 (treatment initiation) in the sarcopenic group; B) Transition probabilities from state 1 (treatment initiation) in the non-sarcopenic group; C) Probability of death after the development of any-grade irAEs in the sarcopenic group; D) Probability of death after the development of any-grade irAEs in the sarcopenic group.

C)

Probability of death after the development of an irAE in the sarcopenic group

D)

Probability of death after the development of an irAE in the non-sarcopenic group

Table A.2. Sensitivity Analysis of the Association Between Sarcopenia and Overall Survival, Incorporating Immune-Related Adverse Events as a Time-Dependent Covariate, as well as the interaction between irAEs.

Sub analysis	Variable	HR	LCI	UCI	P value
Severe irAEs	Sarcopenia	1.13	0.71	1.78	0.598
	irAE	3.42	1.84	6.36	<0.001
	irAE*Sarcopenia	0.28	0.14	0.57	<0.001
Any-grade irAEs	Sarcopenia	1.25	0.84	1.86	0.265
	irAE	1.08	0.60	1.92	0.802
	irAE*Sarcopenia	0.64	0.34	1.19	0.157

